

21GRD08 SoMMet

D7: Report on the comparison of the existing data fusion practices for soil moisture measurements on multiple lateral (from 10^{-1} m to 10^3 m and to depths of up to 1 metre) and temporal (from hours to days) scales to assess the soil moisture with traceable relative uncertainty of 20 % or better

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Deliverable **D7** of project 21GRD08 SoMMet

Report on the comparison of the existing data fusion practices for soil moisture measurements on multiple lateral (from 10^{-1} m to 10^3 m and to depths of up to 1 metre) and temporal (from hours to days) scales to assess the soil moisture with traceable relative uncertainty of 20 % or better

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Glossary

BME: Bayesian Maximum Entropy – A Bayesian data fusion framework that incorporates prior knowledge and entropy principles.

Covariance Matrix (Σ): A matrix representing the spatial covariance between pairs of observations, used in Kriging and other statistical models.

CRNS: Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensor – Instrument that estimate soil moisture by detecting neutrons generated by cosmic rays interacting with hydrogen atoms in the soil.

DL-ML: Deep Learning – A subset of ML using neural networks with multiple layers to model complex patterns.

EO: Earth Observation – Remote sensing techniques using satellite or airborne platforms to monitor Earth's surface.

IDW: Inverse Distance Weighting – An interpolation method where closer points have more influence on the estimated value.

Kriging: A geostatistical interpolation method that provides the best linear unbiased prediction of spatial variables.

LWF: Linear Weighted Fusion – A data fusion technique that combines multiple sources using weights based on reliability or uncertainty.

MAE: Mean Absolute Error – A metric for evaluating prediction accuracy, calculated as the average absolute difference between predicted and observed values.

ML: Machine Learning – A field of artificial intelligence that enables systems to learn patterns from data and make predictions.

NN: Neural Network – A computational model inspired by the human brain, used in deep learning to capture complex relationships.

PCC: Pearson Correlation Coefficient – A measure of linear correlation between two variables.

PDF: Probability Density Function – A function that describes the likelihood of a random variable taking on a particular value.

PS: Point-Scale – Measurements taken at a specific location, typically using in situ sensors.

RF: Random Forest – An ensemble ML method using multiple decision trees for regression or classification.

RL-ML: Reinforcement Learning – ML technique where models learn optimal actions through trial and error based on rewards.

RMSE: Root Mean Square Error – A metric for evaluating the accuracy of predictions, calculated as the square root of the average squared differences between predicted and observed values.

RS: Remote Sensing – The acquisition of information about an object or phenomenon without making physical contact, often via satellites or aircraft.

SL-ML: Supervised Learning – ML technique using labelled data to train models for prediction.

SM: Soil Moisture – The water content held in the soil, critical for hydrological, agricultural, and climate processes.

Triple Collocation (TC): A statistical method to estimate the uncertainty characteristics of three independent datasets without requiring a reference truth.

uSL-ML: Unsupervised Learning – ML technique that identifies patterns in unlabelled data, often used for clustering or dimensionality reduction.

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Summary

This document, deliverable D7, is the seventh of eight technical deliverables of the project 21GRD08 SoMMet (hereafter: SoMMet). The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States (Funder name: European Partnership on Metrology; Funder ID: 10.13039/100019599; Grant number: 21GRD08 SoMMet)

The deliverable D7 is related to SoMMet Task 4.1, *Definition of data fusion methods for soil moisture measurements on multiple scales*. The document provides a literature review of methods for data fusion in soil moisture (SM) measurements across multiple lateral scales (from 10^{-1} m to 10^3 m and to depths of up to 1 metre) and temporal scales (from hours to days).

A general definition of data fusion is “*a formal framework in which are expressed means and tools for the alliance of data originating from different sources. It aims at obtaining information of greater quality; the exact definition of ‘greater quality’ will depend upon the application*” (Wald, 1999).

As it covers a wide domain, extensive literature has been produced on this topic. In this report, we have not attempted to provide an exhaustive list of references or a comprehensive discussion of all methods. Instead, we have selectively highlighted a few key approaches to introduce the current state of the art in the integrative use of SM data, i.e. geostatistical, Bayesian, minimum variance and machine learning methods. The key aspects of each method are presented, and their advantages and limitations are discussed. Finally, suitable approaches are selected for implementation and testing in Task 4.2., *Implementation of data fusion of soil moisture measurements on multiple scales*.

1 Introduction

SM is a crucial climate variable that significantly influences hydrological and atmospheric processes across multiple spatial scales—local, regional, and global. SM plays a vital role in land-atmosphere feedback loops, affecting weather and climate timescales. It governs the partitioning of incoming radiation flux into latent, sensible heat and ground heat fluxes, which in turn impact evapotranspiration, precipitation, runoff, subsurface flow, and infiltration (Seneviratne et al., 2010). Additionally, SM is intimately involved in the feedback between climate and vegetation, influencing soil microbial respiration, biogeochemical cycles, streamflow, crop yield, dust generation, and disease transmission (Rahmati et al., 2024).

SM measurement is primarily conducted using *in situ* sensors and remote sensing (RS) satellites. *In situ* sensors can capture SM data at both point and intermediate scales. Point scale (PS) sampling methods include thermo-gravimetric techniques and handheld and automated probes such as Time Domain Reflectometry and Capacitance Probes. The intermediate scale is primarily measured using Cosmic Ray Neutron Sensors (CRNS).

RS techniques encompass proximal, airborne, and satellite-based approaches. However, only satellite measurements can obtain continuous and spatially consistent streams of SM observations.

The main difference between SM measurement techniques lies in the scale at which they operate. Specifically, the scale of SM measurements can be defined by three components: spacing, extent, and support. "Spacing" refers to the distance between individual measurement points; "extent" denotes the total area covered by the measurements; and "support" indicates the specific area represented by each measurement (Western and Blöschl, 1999).

Point scale (PS) sensors typically have a limited horizontal support, ranging from 5 to 30 cm. In contrast, CRNS offer a broader horizontal support, typically between 100 and 300 meters (Köhli et al., 2015). *In situ* techniques are usually deployed as networks of stations, with spacing that can vary from a few hundred meters to several tens of kilometres. Consequently, the coverage area, or extent, depends on the spacing and the number of stations.

On the other hand, satellite estimates of SM typically have a spacing, which is the distance between individual data points or pixels in the image, ranging from meters to tens of kilometres. The resolution, or support, is usually twice the spacing. For Earth observation (EO) SM products, the extent can reach continental or even global coverage and is periodic in time, thus providing regular time series of SM fields.

Traditionally, the role of *in situ* observations of SM has been to serve as benchmarks to assess the quality of RS products. However, there are often systematic differences between the assumed reference (*in situ* observations) and the RS SM products. These differences arise from several factors. First, *in situ* observations are typically local-scale measurements, meaning they represent SM at a particular site. In contrast, EO SM products normally provide estimates over large areas, resulting in discrepancies in support (resolution) and extent (coverage). Second, *in situ* sensors measure SM at specific depths, which may vary from one sensor to another, while satellite retrievals often provide integrated SM measurements over a depth range. Differences in sensing depths can result in inconsistencies between the two data sources. Third, the algorithms used to retrieve SM

from satellite data rely on various variables to model the land surface, including soil properties, vegetation cover, and atmospheric conditions. Limited or inaccurate parameterisation can introduce uncertainties in the satellite SM estimates.

In the Task 3 activities (Comparison and harmonisation of soil moisture observation methods on multiple spatial and temporal scales) of the SoMMet project, the potential systematic differences between PS, CRNS and RS have been thoroughly investigated. To address the inherent discrepancies, strategies aimed at ensuring more consistent SM measurements across various scales have been assessed.

Furthermore, the abundance of multiscale SM data presents an exceptional opportunity for the scientific community to deepen the understanding of SM dynamics across different scales. Consequently, a further key research objective is to optimally integrate SM data from various instruments while distinguishing between measurement uncertainties from different devices and the inherent spatial dynamics of the SM distribution. To this aim, the objectives of SoMMet's Task 4 activities are i) to review and compare different fusion methods for soil moisture measurements on multiple spatial and temporal scales and ii) to provide examples of data fusion of multi-scale soil moisture measurements. The following presents a review of the SM data fusion.

The methods of SM data fusion reviewed are:

- **Geostatistical** data fusion integrates spatial information from multiple sources to generate a single, comprehensive spatial dataset. This process reduces uncertainty by leveraging the strengths of each data source while mitigating limitations through statistical modelling. The objective is to produce the most accurate spatial representation by accounting for spatial dependencies and quantifying uncertainties.
- **Bayesian** data fusion uses probabilistic models based on Bayes' theorem to integrate data while explicitly accounting for uncertainties. It treats different data sources as probability distributions and updates prior knowledge with new observations. Multiple sources are combined to make more accurate inferences to update beliefs about the quantity of interest.
- **Minimum Variance** technique combines information from multiple sensors or sources in a way that minimises the variance of the resulting estimate. It aims to produce the most reliable estimate by leveraging the strengths of individual sources and reducing the impact of uncertainties or errors.
- **Machine Learning**: is a field of artificial intelligence (AI) that enables systems to learn and improve from data without being explicitly programmed, by identifying patterns and making predictions or decisions.

2 Geostatistical methods

2.1 Statistical Framework

The approach is grounded in geostatistical modelling, which formalises spatial correlations and relationships among datasets with varying resolutions. The fusion process incorporates probabilistic methods to systematically manage discrepancies arising from different measurement scales, ensuring consistency in the final dataset. A fundamental challenge in this integration is the change of support problem, which occurs when combining data collected at different spatial resolutions. Interpolation techniques like Kriging are used to estimate values at unsampled locations (e.g. Fuhg et al., 2021, for an extended review).

2.2 Kriging

Geostatistical techniques analyse spatial autocorrelation, assessing how values at one location influence those nearby. This ensures a coherent spatial representation by interpolating missing values using known data points. Kriging provides a statistically sound way to estimate values at unsampled locations by considering the spatial relationships within the data, making it a valuable tool in geostatistical data fusion for enhancing spatial accuracy and completeness.

Here, we briefly review the modelling of spatial scales and the parameterisation of the spatial covariance matrix adopted in ordinary Kriging (Cressie, 1988). Observed spatial data are considered a random process ($\{Z(s), s \in D\}$) that samples a hidden geophysical random variable ($\{Y(s): s \in D\}$). Z , Y , and s (spatial locations) are real and defined on a two- or three-dimensional space (D). The following linear model links the two processes:

$$Z(s) = Y(s) + \varepsilon(s) \quad (1)$$

$$Y(s) = \mu(s) + W(s) + \eta(s) \quad (2)$$

where:

- $\mu(s)$ represents the deterministic mean structure (large-scale variation),
- $W(s)$ is a zero-mean, continuous, stationary random process (smooth small-scale variation),
- $\eta(s)$ is a zero-mean, stationary process, independent of $W(s)$ (microscale variations),
- $\varepsilon(s)$ is a zero-mean white noise process and independent of $W(s)$ and $\eta(s)$.

Based on the above spatial modelling, Kriging yields the best linear unbiased predictor, given by $\hat{Y}(s_0) = \alpha Z$ at location s_0 , where α is the vector of unknown linear coefficients estimated from the observations and associated uncertainty. The optimal prediction is obtained by minimizing the mean square error, which requires inversion of the covariance matrix ($\Sigma = \text{cov}(Z(s_i), Z(s_j))$).

In summary, Kriging estimates values of $(Y(s))$ at unmeasured locations based on the spatial relationship of sampled points by modelling spatial covariance (Σ). Unlike simpler interpolation methods, Kriging also provides an estimate of uncertainty, allowing users to assess the reliability of predictions.

The above-described approach can naturally handle the change of support problem, which arises when spatial data collected at one scale is used to infer or predict values at a different scale or resolution. Statistical properties, such as variance, may change when transitioning between different spatial resolutions, requiring adjustments to maintain accuracy (Nguyen et al., 2012).

2.3 Fusion Process

In data fusion, the above-described procedure is extended to the case of two (or more) realisations, Z_1 and Z_2 . The objective is to derive an optimal estimate of the underlying process. Formally, equations (1) and (2) can be defined for N , Z_k ($k=1,2\dots N$) processes. The associated covariance matrix is:

$$\Sigma_{kl} = \text{cov}(Z_k, Z_l) \quad (3)$$

For ($N=2$), the data-fusion predictor is a linear combination of Z_1 and Z_2 :

$$\hat{Y}(s) = \alpha_1 Z_1 + \alpha_2 Z_2 \quad (4)$$

where the optimal solution is obtained by minimising the mean square error $\langle (Y - \hat{Y}(s))^2 \rangle$. The solution is a function of the covariance matrix Σ_{12} .

Significant progress has been made in tailoring the method to the needs of applications handling large amounts of data in space and time. In such cases, the inversion of large matrices is a severe problem. Various evolutions of ordinary Kriging have been developed to address the increase in spatial data.

In conclusion, Kriging is a powerful geostatistical interpolation method, but it does have advantages and several limitations. In the following, they are summarised.

2.4 Advantages of Kriging

- Provides optimal and unbiased predictions, e.g. (Virdee and Kottegoda, 1984).
- Quantifies uncertainty, making results more reliable, e.g. (Wang and Zuo, 2024).
- Adapts to spatial heterogeneity, improving accuracy over simpler interpolation methods, e.g. (Lam, 1983).

2.5 Limitations of Kriging

- Stationarity Assumption – Kriging assumes that the spatial process is stationary, meaning that statistical properties (such as mean and variance) remain constant across the study area. If the data exhibits strong trends or non-stationary behaviour, Kriging may produce inaccurate results, e.g. (Giraldo et al., 2023).
- Isotropy Requirement – Standard Kriging assumes isotropy, meaning that spatial correlation is uniform in all directions. In reality, many spatial phenomena exhibit anisotropy, where correlation varies depending on direction. Specialised Kriging methods, such as anisotropic Kriging, are required to address this, e.g. (Creutin and Obled, 1982).
- Data Density and Distribution – Kriging performs best when there is a sufficient number of well-distributed data points. If the dataset is sparse or unevenly distributed, the interpolation may be unreliable, leading to large uncertainties in predictions, e.g. (Lam, 1983).
- Computational Complexity – Kriging involves solving a system of linear equations, which can be computationally intensive, especially for large datasets. The complexity increases with the number of data points, making it impractical for very large-scale applications without optimisation techniques, e.g. (Alizadeh et al., 2020).
- Variogram Estimation Challenges – The accuracy of Kriging depends on a well-defined variogram, which models spatial correlation. Estimating a reliable variogram requires careful selection of parameters and sufficient data. Poor variogram estimation can lead to misleading results, e.g. (Oliver and Webster, 2014).
- Sensitivity to Outliers – Kriging is sensitive to outliers in the dataset. Extreme values can disproportionately influence predictions, leading to skewed results. Preprocessing techniques, such as outlier removal or robust Kriging variants, may be necessary, e.g., (Wang et al., 2022).
- Limited Applicability for Non-Gaussian Data – Kriging assumes that the underlying spatial process follows a Gaussian distribution. If the data exhibits non-Gaussian behaviour, alternative methods such as indicator Kriging or Bayesian Kriging may be more appropriate, e.g., (Cressie et al., 2022).

Despite these limitations, Kriging remains a widely used and effective geostatistical method, particularly when applied with appropriate modifications to address specific challenges. Indeed, to address some limitations, the method has further evolved, developing different types of Kriging over the years, e.g.:

- Ordinary Kriging – Assumes a constant but unknown mean across the study area, e.g., (Oliver and Webster, 2014).
- Simple Kriging – Uses a known mean value for predictions, e.g., (Bostan, 2017).

- Universal Kriging – Accounts for trends in the data by incorporating external variables, e.g., (Heuvelink et al., 2006).
- Co-Kriging – Uses multiple correlated datasets to improve predictions, e.g., (Vann and Geoval, 1998).
- Indicator Kriging – Applies categorical data for probabilistic mapping, e.g., (Carvalho and Deutsch, 2017).

2.6 Examples of studies applying Geostatistical Data Fusion to soil moisture measurements

- Ochsner, T.E., Linde, E., Haffner, M. and Dong, J., 2018. Mesoscale Soil Moisture Patterns Revealed Using a Sparse In Situ Network and Regression Kriging. *Water Resources Research*, 54(10), pp.8053-8068, (Ochsner et al., 2019):

This study addresses the challenge of observing soil moisture patterns at mesoscale lengths (1-100 km), which are crucial for hydrological, ecological, and agricultural processes. Existing monitoring systems, such as satellite-based radiometers and sparse in situ networks, often have footprints that are either too large or too small to capture these patterns effectively. This gap complicates the calibration and validation of hydrologic models and soil moisture satellites. The study proposes using geostatistical techniques, specifically regression kriging, to map dynamic mesoscale soil moisture patterns. The system developed utilizes daily soil moisture data from the Oklahoma Mesonet, sand content estimates from the NRCS Soil Survey Geographic Database, and an antecedent precipitation index from NWS multisensor precipitation estimates. A multiple linear regression model is fitted daily to the observed data, and the residuals are used in a semivariogram estimation and kriging routine to produce daily statewide soil moisture maps at 5-, 25-, and 60-cm depths with 800-m resolution. Over three years, this system has revealed complex, dynamic, and depth-specific mesoscale patterns influenced by soil texture and precipitation, achieving a mean absolute error of $\leq 0.0576 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ across all depths.

- Zhang, J., Li, X., Yang, R., Liu, Q., Zhao, L. and Dou, B., 2017. An Extended Kriging Method to Interpolate Near-Surface Soil Moisture Data Measured by Wireless Sensor Networks. *Sensors*, 17(6), p.1390, (Zhang et al., 2017):

Traditional Kriging methods, such as Co-kriging and Kriging with external drift (KED), struggle to interpolate near-surface soil moisture measured by wireless sensor networks (WSN) due to soil moisture heterogeneity and low correlation with auxiliary variables. This study introduces an Extended Kriging method that incorporates spectral variables from remote sensing images, operating in a combined spatial and spectral space. Applied to WSN-measured soil moisture data from the HiWATER campaign (10 June to 15 July 2012), Extended Kriging generated daily maps. Compared to Ordinary Kriging (OK), Co-kriging, and KED, Extended Kriging provided more spatial details and achieved the lowest Root Mean

Square Error (RMSE), demonstrating its effectiveness in integrating remote sensing information with ground measurements for soil moisture interpolation.

3 Bayesian methods

3.1 Key Concepts

A general formulation of Bayesian data fusion methodology has been developed by (Bogaert and Fasbender, 2007). Here, a brief description of the main concepts is summarised.

The initial common assumption of the various approaches is that the variables of interest, denoted as a random real vector $Y(s) \in \mathfrak{R}^n$, with $s \in \mathfrak{R}^d$, are hidden (they cannot be directly observed). Instead, the observations, denoted as a random vector $Z(s)$, are functionally related to Y through additive random uncertainties ε , like

$$Z = g(Y) + \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

Z and ε (and consequently Y) are considered of the continuous type, though all results can be extended to discrete or mixed random variables.

Under the assumption that the joint multivariate probability distribution function (*pdf*) of Y and ε are known, denoted $f(Y)$ and $f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon)$, that Y and ε are independent, and that ε is zero mean, using Bayes's theorem and (5) it is possible to derive the conditional probability density function (*pdf*) of vector Y given the observed variables (Bogaert and Fasbender, 2007), as

$$f(Y | Z) = \frac{1}{A} f_\varepsilon(Z - g(Y)) f(Y) \quad (6)$$

where A is a normalisation constant. The prediction of Y at a specific location s_0 can be obtained as the marginal conditional pdf at s_0 , which is computed by integrating (6) over all the other variables

$$f(Y_0 | Z) = \frac{1}{A} \int \cdots \int f(Y) f_\varepsilon(Z - g(Y)) dY_1 \cdots dY_n \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) is a remarkable example of how Bayesian inference offers a solid scheme to incorporate prior knowledge and uncertainty, represented by Y and ε *pdfs*, into the fusion process, leading to more robust and reliable estimations.

3.2 Data Fusion

Let us consider having two observations (Z_1, Z_2) of the variable Y related through the following equations

$$Z_1 = g_1(Y) + \varepsilon_1 \quad (8)$$

$$Z_2 = g_2(Y) + \varepsilon_2 \quad (9)$$

Under the assumption that the error random variables (ε_1 , ε_2) are zero mean and independent of Y , (7) can be generalised as (Bogaert and Fasbender, 2007)

$$f(Y_0 | Z_1, Z_2) = \frac{1}{A} \int \cdots \int f(Y) f_{\varepsilon_1}(Z_1 - g_1(Y)) f_{\varepsilon_2}(Z_2 - g_2(Y)) dY_1 \cdots dY_n \quad (10)$$

Bayesian and geostatistical methods can adopt a similar statistical modelling of the relationship between the observations (Z) and the geophysical variable (Y). The main difference is that while geostatistical methods leverage correlations, Bayesian methods use Bayesian inference. A key advantage is its ability to incorporate prior knowledge and uncertainty, represented in (10) by the probability density functions of Y and ε , into the fusion process, leading to more robust and reliable estimations. However, a primary disadvantage is the computational cost, particularly with complex models and large datasets.

In the following, we briefly review the advantages and limitations of the approach.

3.3 Advantages of Bayesian data fusion

- Incorporate prior knowledge - Bayesian methods allow for the incorporation of prior beliefs or information about the data, which can be crucial when data is limited or noisy, e.g., (Boluki et al., 2017).
- Handle uncertainty - Bayesian data fusion explicitly accounts for uncertainties in the input data and fusion process, leading to more reliable estimations and inferences, e.g., (Agostinelli and Greco, 2013).
- Intuitive and informative results - Bayesian methods provide probabilistic statements about parameters, making the interpretation of results more intuitive and informative, e.g., (Marchant and Ramos, 2014; McKenzie, 1994).
- Flexibility and adaptability - Bayesian approaches are versatile and can be adapted to various data types and fusion scenarios, e.g., (Ross et al., 2007).
- Model comparison and selection - Bayesian methods offer tools for comparing different models and selecting the most appropriate one for a given task, e.g., (Cao and Wang, 2014).

3.4 Limitations of Bayesian data fusion

- Computational cost - Bayesian analysis can be computationally expensive, especially when dealing with complex models or large datasets. This can be a barrier for certain application, e.g. (Marin et al., 2012).

- Subjectivity in prior specification - The choice of prior distribution can introduce a degree of subjectivity into the analysis. Poorly specified priors can lead to biased results, e.g. (Menin, 2024).
- Model complexity - Bayesian models can be complex to design and implement, requiring expertise in both statistical modeling and programming, e.g. (Spiegelhalter et al., 2002).
- Interpretability challenges - While probabilistic statements are generally more intuitive, they can also be more difficult to interpret and communicate effectively than point estimates, e.g. (de Santana et al., 2007).
- Sensitivity to model assumptions - The accuracy of Bayesian data fusion relies on the validity of the underlying model assumptions. Incorrectly specified models can lead to misleading results, e.g. (Goslings, 2022).

In fact, there are different methods within Bayesian Data Fusion, each with its own strengths and weaknesses. Some prominent examples include naive Bayesian fusion, federated Kalman filtering, and methods leveraging data-driven models. These approaches differ in how they handle uncertainty, prior information, and the nature of the data being fused.

Here is a more detailed look at some common Bayesian Data Fusion methods:

- Naive Bayesian Fusion. This is a simpler approach where each data source is treated as conditionally independent, meaning the presence of one source does not affect the probability of another, e.g. (Altıncay, 2005).
- Federated Kalman Filtering. This method extends the Kalman filter, a common tool for state estimation, to handle multiple sensor inputs and potentially different dynamics across sensors, e.g. (Fan et al., 2025).
- Data-Driven Models. Some Bayesian data fusion methods incorporate data-driven models, such as machine learning algorithms, to learn the relationships between data sources and improve fusion accuracy, e.g. (See, 2008).
- Hierarchical Bayesian Fusion. This approach allows for a more flexible and adaptive fusion framework, where the reliability of each individual data source is assessed and incorporated into the fusion process, e.g. (Kou et al., 2024).
- Bayesian Networks. Bayesian networks can model complex relationships between multiple data sources and their associated uncertainties, e.g. (Zhang and Ji, 2006).
- Maximum Entropy (ME) and Maximum Likelihood (ML) Estimation. These methods are often used in conjunction with Bayesian methods; ME assigns a probability law to an unknown quantity when macroscopic data is available, while ML estimates the parameters of a probability law when microscopic data is available, e.g. (Han et al., 2020).

3.5 Examples of studies applying Bayesian approaches to fuse soil moisture measurements

- Aguirre, C. A., Rondán, G. A., Sedano, C. G., Rut, T., & Cardozo, M. (2025). "Bayesian Data Fusion Framework for Soil Moisture Interpolation in Entre Ríos, Argentina: Analysis of Topographic Indices." (Aguirre et al., 2025).

This study focuses on estimating soil moisture content, a crucial variable for crop growth and yield prediction. Traditional simulation models often overlook spatial variability, simulating soil moisture for an average plant without considering differences across the field. Relief, or topography, can explain this variability. To address this, the study combines spatial interpolations from sampling campaigns with Bayesian data fusion techniques to create soil moisture maps in the root zone. Measurements were taken in the first half of 2021 and the second half of 2022. Analysis of topographic indices revealed that the inverse topographic moisture index and digital terrain model best explain soil moisture variability. By integrating these indices with Ordinary Kriging interpolation results through Bayesian data fusion, the study found improved soil moisture estimates. An independent data set confirmed that this method outperformed using Ordinary Kriging alone.

- Han, L., Wang, C., Liu, Q., Wang, G., Yu, T., Gu, X. and Zhang, Y., 2020. Soil moisture mapping based on multi-source fusion of optical, near-infrared, thermal infrared, and digital elevation model data via the Bayesian maximum entropy framework. *Remote Sensing*, 12(23), p.3916, (Han et al., 2020):

This paper presents a method for soil moisture mapping using a combination of optical, near-infrared, and thermal infrared data from Landsat 8 and ASTER GDEM data, based on the Bayesian maximum entropy (BME) framework. The study involves three stages:

- General Knowledge Construction: Using the maximum entropy principle, a Lagrange multiplier is introduced to represent prior knowledge.
- Principal Component Analysis (PCA): PCA extracts three principal components from the multi-source data. A fuzzy probability matrix approximates the probability relationships, generating soft data based on weight coefficients and coordinates.
- Soil Moisture Mapping: Combining general knowledge, prior information, hard data (HD), and soft data (SD) using the Bayesian conditioning rule to complete the mapping.

The method was validated against the ordinary kriging (OK) method. Results showed that the BME framework provided more detailed soil moisture maps with higher accuracy (RMSE = 0.0423 cm³/cm³, MAE = 0.0399 cm³/cm³, PCC = 0.7846), effectively addressing overestimation and underestimation issues. This approach demonstrates the potential of the BME framework for accurate soil moisture mapping using multi-source data.

- Kathuria, D., Mohanty, B.P. and Katzfuss, M., 2019. Multiscale data fusion for surface soil moisture estimation: A spatial hierarchical approach. *Water Resources Research*, 55(12), pp.10443-10465 (Kathuria et al., 2019).

Surface soil moisture (SSM) is a crucial climate variable influencing hydrologic and atmospheric processes at various spatial scales. The recent proliferation of SSM datasets

offers significant potential for understanding these dynamics. However, fusing SSM data from different instruments faces challenges due to varying spatial resolutions, inherent spatial variability, and measurement errors. This study introduces a data fusion scheme using a Bayesian spatial hierarchical model (SHM), which combines geostatistical approaches with hierarchical modeling to address these issues. The scheme is demonstrated by fusing point, airborne, and satellite data for a watershed in Manitoba, Canada, known for high spatial variability. The proposed method effectively assimilates and predicts SSM distribution across different scales while accounting for measurement errors. Further validation in diverse hydroclimates and surface heterogeneity is needed for broader applicability.

4 Minimum Variance methods

Minimum Variance methods aim to determine the optimal weights assigned to different data sources to achieve the most stable and accurate fusion. While these methods can be framed within a probabilistic context, they can also be approached deterministically, focusing on minimising the variance of the output without explicitly handling uncertainty.

Various techniques implement minimum variance data fusion, such as Least Squares, Linear Weight Fusion, and Non-linear Fusion. Least Squares minimises the sum of squared errors, while Linear Weight Fusion combines data sources using weights based on their uncertainty or reliability. Non-linear Fusion, on the other hand, allows for more complex relationships between inputs and their contributions, potentially using non-linear functions or algorithms to determine and combine weights. Non-linear Fusion can be more complex to implement and requires more computational resources.

4.1 Linear Weight Fusion

Linear Weight Fusion (LWF) is considered a robust, computationally efficient, and well-understood method for fusing forecasts. Its roots trace back to the seminal paper by Bates & Granger (1969), which investigates the benefits of combining multiple forecasts to improve prediction accuracy. Bates and Granger challenge the common practice of selecting the best single forecast and discarding others.

Given two sets of unbiased forecasts, denoted f_1 and f_2 , having variance σ_1^2 and σ_2^2 , the combined forecast would be obtained by a linear combination of the two sets of forecasts, giving a weight k to the first set of forecasts and a weight $(1 - k)$ to the second set, thus making the combined forecast unbiased. The optimal weight (minimising the total variance) is

$$k = \frac{\sigma_2^2 - \rho\sigma_1\sigma_2}{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2 - 2\rho\sigma_1\sigma_2} \quad (11)$$

where ρ is the correlation coefficient between the two forecasts.

In a subsequent study, Granger and Ramanathan (1984) focus on the benefits of combining multiple forecasting methods, rather than relying on a single, potentially "best" model. By combining forecasts, one can effectively "hedge" against the inherent uncertainty of individual models,

potentially achieving better overall accuracy than the best individual model. This approach is often seen as a way to create a more robust and reliable forecasting system by leveraging the strengths of different models. Granger's work, alongside others like Bates, has popularised the idea of forecast combination and spawned a rich literature on the topic (e.g. Clemen, 1989; Wasko et al., 2013).

In fact, LWF can be regarded as a general data fusion framework where values from different sources are combined using a weighted average. The key steps include:

- Forecast Generation: Obtain multiple forecasts from different models or sources.
- Weight Calculation: Determine the optimal weights for each forecast based on historical performance, reliability, accuracy, or other relevant factors.
- Combination: Combine the forecasts using the calculated weights to produce a single, improved forecast.

In this view, LWF can be integrated with a variety of techniques, leveraging their strengths to significantly enhance the accuracy and reliability of the fused data and adapting the method to a broad range of use cases.

4.2 Linear Weight Fusion and Triple Collocation

For instance, LWF can be applied in conjunction with Triple Collocation (TC), which estimates the uncertainties and correlations of different forecasts, allowing for a more informed weighting of these sources in the linear combination. In particular, TC quantifies the uncertainties and correlation among three independent datasets without requiring a true, ground-truth dataset. By analysing the relationships between these three datasets, TC provides insights into the individual uncertainties and inter-dependencies of each dataset. In the context of data fusion, TC helps to assess the quality of different forecast models and identify potential biases or correlations (Xie et al., 2022).

4.3 Linear Weight Fusion and Interpolation Techniques

LWF can be combined with interpolation techniques. In fact, some interpolation methods, like Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW), inherently use a linearly weighted combination of nearby points to estimate values at unobserved locations. Therefore, LWF can be seen as a broader framework that encompasses interpolation, allowing for various weighting schemes and applications beyond just spatial estimation.

To combine LWF with IDW, the following steps can be foreseen:

- Determine IDW Weights: Calculate the weights for each data point based on their distance from the point of interest using the inverse distance formula:

$$w_i = \frac{1}{d_i} \tag{12}$$

where w_i is the weight for the i -th data point, d_i is the distance from the point of interest.

- Calculate LWF Weights: Determine the weights for each data source based on their reliability or uncertainty.
- Combine Weights: Integrate the IDW weights with the LWF weights. One approach is to multiply the IDW weights by the LWF weights to get a combined weight for each data point:

$$w_{\text{combined},i} = w_{\text{IDW},i} \times w_{\text{LWF},i} \quad (13)$$

- Fuse Data: Use the combined weights to fuse the data from different sources. The fused value at the point of interest can be calculated as:

$$V_{\text{fused}} = \sum_i w_{\text{combined},i} \cdot V_i \quad (14)$$

Where V_i is the value from the i -th data point.

Such an approach is particularly useful in integrating data sources with different extents and potential spatial gaps, as it occurs when fusing EO and *in situ* SM data. In this case, to build a combined product filling the gaps, it is crucial to account for the intrinsic uncertainty of the data source and the location of the source.

LWF can also be used in conjunction with other interpolation methods, such as:

- Spline Interpolation: Where LWF could be used to combine the results of different spline interpolations or to assign different weights to different splines based on their accuracy.
- Kriging: Where LWF could be used to combine the results of multiple kriging models or to incorporate other data sources into the kriging process.

4.4 Examples of studies applying Linear Weight Fusion to fuse soil moisture products

Here are four references that use LWF to fuse soil moisture products:

- Nabi, M. M., Senyurek, V., Kurum, M., & Gurbuz, A. C. (2024). Best linear unbiased estimators for fusion of multiple CYGNSS soil moisture products. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing* (Nabi et al., 2024).

This study explores different fusion algorithms, including Linear Weight Fusion, to combine distinct global CYGNSS-based soil moisture products. The results demonstrate notable performance enhancements when combining different soil moisture data products.

- Lv, A., Yang, X., Zhang, W., & Han, Y. (2025). Integrated soil moisture fusion for enhanced agricultural drought monitoring in China. *Agricultural Water Management*, 311, 109401 (Lv et al., 2025):

This research developed an improved soil moisture dataset (Merged-SM) using Triple Collocation and Linear Weight Fusion methods to fuse soil moisture data from ERA5-Land, ESA CCI, and MERRA-2. The dataset was validated against in-situ data and applied to investigate the spatiotemporal dynamics of agricultural droughts across China.

- Xie, Q., Jia, L., Menenti, M., & Hu, G. (2022). Global soil moisture data fusion by Triple Collocation Analysis from 2011 to 2018. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), 687 (Xie et al., 2022):

The study creates a Global Daily-scale Soil Moisture Fusion Dataset (GDSMFD) with 25 km spatial resolution for the period 2011-2018 using Triple Collocation and Linear Weight Fusion methods. The dataset was evaluated against in situ soil moisture measurements from ten ground observation networks and compared with pre-fusion SM products. Results showed that GDSMFD was consistent with in situ measurements, with a minimum root mean square error of 0.036 cm³/cm³. It also had good global coverage, with a mean Global Coverage Fraction (GCF) of 0.672 and a maximum GCF of 0.837.

- Funk, C., Peterson, P., Landsfeld, M., Pedreros, D., Verdin, J., Shukla, S., Husak, G., Rowland, J., Harrison, L., Hoell, A., & Michaelsen, J. (2015). The climate hazards infrared precipitation with stations—A new environmental record for monitoring extremes. *Scientific Data*, 2(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2015.66> (Funk et al., 2015).

The study focuses the quasi-global (50°S-50°N), high resolution (0.05°), daily, pentadal, and monthly Climate Hazards group Infrared Precipitation with Stations (CHIRPS) dataset. The paper presents the CHIRPS algorithm, global and regional validation results, and show how CHIRPS can be used to quantify the hydrologic impacts of decreasing precipitation and rising air temperatures in the Greater Horn of Africa. CHIRPS uses a three-step process, first generating infrared precipitation (IRP) estimates from satellite data, then adjusting these IRP estimates using a climatology, and finally blending the adjusted satellite data with rain gauge observations using an inverse distance weighting method. By combining satellite and in-situ data, CHIRPS aims to produce more accurate and reliable precipitation estimates than either data source alone.

These references provide a comprehensive overview of the application of Linear Weight Fusion in fusing soil moisture products, demonstrating its effectiveness in various contexts and regions.

5 Machine Learning methods

Machine Learning (ML) method is one of the techniques of modern Artificial Intelligence (AI) commonly applied in big data, in statistics, medicine and many other sciences, including natural science. ML process empowers computers to learn from data without explicit programming. The method is used for different purposes as prediction, data gap filling and data improvements. Taking into account the specification of the technique, the ML can be divided into: Supervised machine

learning, Unsupervised machine learning, Reinforcement learning and Deep learning (Udousoro, 2020). In general, the ML process is divided into four basic steps (which are suited depending on the ML technique used in particular task):

- **Data preparation:** Data preparation is one of the most challenging and time-consuming tasks in any ML process. In this step, all necessary data is collected from various sources, pre-processed and then split into a training and a test set for further processing.
- **Model Building:** This involves choosing a representation or hypothesis, which is essentially the form or structure your model will take.
- **Model Training:** The built model is trained by feeding it with the training data iteratively. In each iteration, the model tries to become increasingly accurate by decreasing its uncertainty. Training is stopped when a certain number of finite iterations is reached or when other pre-defined stopping criteria are met.
- **Model Evaluation:** The trained model is evaluated against a test set for determining its performance and finding ways to improve it.

5.1 Supervised Learning

Supervised Learning (SL-ML) is the most common category of ML. Algorithms are trained on labelled data, where each input is paired with a corresponding output value. During training, the model iteratively adjusts its internal parameters using optimisation techniques like Gradient Descent in ML to minimise the difference between predicted outputs and actual labels. SL-ML aims to train the algorithm to find the connection between inputs and outputs and apply this knowledge to make precise predictions on new data. In SM studies, the SL-ML is mainly adopted for improving the spatio-temporal resolution of data.

5.2 Unsupervised Learning

Unsupervised Learning (uSL-ML) uses unlabelled data for extracting patterns, structures, or relationships within it. Unsupervised Learning does not require an explicit input-output relation for training. uSL-ML algorithms use clustering and dimensionality reduction techniques to organise data into groups based on similarities without losing essential information. In the context of SM studies, uSL-ML is mainly adopted for extreme events identification and improvement of SM data by unlabelled auxiliary data.

5.3 Reinforcement Learning

Whereas supervised learning trains models by optimizing them to match ideal exemplars and unsupervised learning algorithms fit themselves to a dataset, reinforcement learning (RL) models are trained holistically through trial and error. RL-ML trains a model to evaluate its environment and take an action that will garner the greatest reward. RL scenarios do not entail the existence of a singular ground truth, but they do entail the existence of “good” and “bad” (or neutral) actions. In the

context of SM studies, the RL-ML is involved in processes when big amount of auxiliary data is applied into the process, and the new data are incorporated during the output evaluation. Method is mostly used for complex systems analysis as global SM assessments.

5.4 Deep Learning

Deep Learning (DL-ML) is a significant type of ML that utilizes deep Neural Networks (NN) or Random Forest (RF) models to address intricate problems rather than the explicitly designed algorithms of traditional ML. The NNs imitate the structure and operation of the human brain, consisting of numerous interconnected layers of neurons. The RF method is an ensemble multiple decision trees model that obtains the optimal predictions by averaging the output of numerous regression trees. The popularity of DL-ML has skyrocketed due to its capability to learn complex patterns automatically. In the context of SM, DL-ML is one of the most important approaches as it allows for improving the results significantly by manipulating the parameters of neural networks used in the process. This method is used basically for generating high resolution SM data as well as for uncertainty improvements.

5.5 Advantages of Machine Learning data fusion

Some specific and general advantages are listed:

- Improved accuracy and insights: ML algorithms have the remarkable ability to learn from the data provided to them. As they receive more data, they continuously refine their models, leading to enhanced accuracy and efficiency in predictions and decision-making without the need for constant reprogramming.
- Predictive analytics: ML excels at forecasting future trends and behaviors by identifying complex non-linear relationships in historical data.
- Scalability: ML systems handle massive datasets effortlessly, making them ideal for large-scale applications.
- Versatility: Machine Learning exhibits exceptional versatility, permeating virtually every sector and facet of modern life.

5.6 Limitations of Machine Learning data fusion

- Data dependency: ML systems are heavily reliant on the quality, quantity, and relevance of data. If the data is insufficient, outdated, or contains biases, the model's predictions and decisions may be flawed. Overfitting or underfitting can significantly impact the reliability of ML systems.
- Time consuming: Processing and training machine learning models can be time-intensive with high computational costs, especially with large datasets.

- Complexity and lack of interpretability: Many ML models, particularly deep learning algorithms, operate as “black boxes,” where their decision-making process is opaque. This lack of transparency makes it difficult to interpret results.

5.7 Examples of studies applying Machine Learning to fuse soil moisture measurements

- Ahmed Samir Abowarda, Liangliang Bai, Caijin Zhang, Di Long, Xueying Li, Qi Huang, Zhangli Sun, Generating surface soil moisture at 30 m spatial resolution using both data fusion and machine learning toward better water resources management at the field scale, *Remote Sensing of Environment*, Volume 255, 2021, 112301, ISSN 0034-4257, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112301> (Abowarda et al., 2021).

In the study, both data fusion and random forest models along with a range of remote sensing, reanalysis, and in situ data were jointly used to generate spatiotemporally continuous surface soil moisture (SSM) at 30 m × 30 m. The downscaled SSM using ESA SMOS and NASA SMAP products as background fields was improved significantly in terms of accuracy and spatial distribution.

- Van der Schalie, R.; De Jeu, R.; Parinussa, R.; Rodríguez-Fernández, N.; Kerr, Y.; Al-Yaari, A.; Wigneron, J.-P.; Drusch, M. The Effect of Three Different Data Fusion Approaches on the Quality of Soil Moisture Retrievals from Multiple Passive Microwave Sensors. *Remote Sens.* 2018, 10, 107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10010107> (van der Schalie et al., 2018)

The three evaluated approaches were developed on 10-year passive microwave data (2003–2013) from two different satellite sensors, i.e., SMOS (2010–2013) and AMSR-E (2003–2011), and are based on a neural network (NN), regressions (REG), and the Land Parameter Retrieval Model (LPRM). The objective is to improve our understanding of L-band-based soil moisture concerning its integration in long-term data records.

- Batchu, V., G. Nearing, and V. Gulshan, 2023: A Deep Learning Data Fusion Model Using Sentinel-1/2, SoilGrids, SMAP, and GLDAS for Soil Moisture Retrieval. *J. Hydrometeor.*, 24, 1789–1823, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JHM-D-22-0118.1> (Batchu et al., 2023)

Develops a deep learning based convolutional-regression model that estimates the volumetric soil moisture content in the top ~5 cm of soil at a resolution of 320m. Input predictors include Sentinel-1 (active radar), Sentinel-2 (optical imagery), and SMAP (passive radar) as well as geophysical variables from SoilGrids and modelled soil moisture fields from GLDAS.

- Singh, A., Gaurav, K. Deep learning and data fusion to estimate surface soil moisture from multi-sensor satellite images. *Sci Rep* 13, 2251 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-28939-9> (Singh and Gaurav, 2023).

The study proposes a new architecture based on a fully connected feed-forward Artificial Neural Network model to estimate surface soil moisture from satellite images on a large alluvial fan of the Kosi River in the Himalayan Foreland.

6 Conclusions

This report has reviewed a range of data fusion techniques for integrating SM measurements across multiple spatial and temporal scales. The methods examined include Geostatistical, Bayesian, Minimum Variance, and Machine Learning approaches, each offering distinct advantages and limitations depending on the application context.

Geostatistical methods, particularly Kriging, provide optimal and unbiased spatial predictions with quantified uncertainty. They are well-suited for handling the change of support problem and have been successfully applied to interpolate SM data across heterogeneous landscapes. However, their reliance on stationarity assumptions and computational complexity in large datasets can limit their scalability.

Bayesian methods offer a probabilistic framework that explicitly incorporates prior knowledge and uncertainty. They are highly flexible and informative, making them valuable for robust SM estimation. Nonetheless, their computational demands and sensitivity to model assumptions pose challenges for operational use, especially in real-time applications.

Machine Learning techniques, including supervised, unsupervised, and deep learning models, demonstrate strong capabilities in pattern recognition, prediction, and data gap filling. These methods are particularly effective in high-resolution mapping and uncertainty reduction. However, they require large, high-quality datasets and often suffer from interpretability issues.

Among the reviewed approaches, Linear Weight Fusion and Interpolation Techniques stand out for their simplicity, computational efficiency, and adaptability. These methods combine data sources using weights derived from reliability, uncertainty, or spatial proximity, making them especially suitable for integrating remote sensing and in situ SM measurements. When paired with interpolation schemes such as Inverse Distance Weighting or Kriging, Linear Weight Fusion techniques can effectively fill spatial gaps and harmonize data from sources with differing resolutions and extents. Their modular nature allows for integration with advanced methods like Triple Collocation, further enhancing the robustness of fused products.

Table I provides a comparative overview of the principal data fusion techniques reviewed in this report. It synthesizes key attributes of each method—including strengths, limitations, and recommended use cases—into a concise format that facilitates method selection and contextual understanding.

In conclusion, Linear Weight Fusion and Interpolation Techniques offer a practical and scalable solution for multi-source SM integration. Their ability to balance data quality and spatial coverage makes them particularly valuable for operational monitoring and climate applications. Future work should focus on refining weighting schemes and exploring hybrid models that combine LWF with probabilistic or machine learning frameworks to further improve accuracy and reliability.

Table 1. Comparison of Data Fusion Techniques for Soil Moisture Integration.

Method	Strengths	Limitations	Best use cases
Geostatistical (Kriging)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimal linear unbiased prediction - Quantifies uncertainty - Handles spatial autocorrelation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assumes stationarity and isotropy - Sensitive to outliers - Computationally intensive for large datasets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interpolation of sparse in situ data - Mapping mesoscale SM patterns
Bayesian	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incorporates prior knowledge - Explicit uncertainty modeling - Flexible and probabilistic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High computational cost - Requires careful prior specification - Complex model design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fusion of heterogeneous datasets - Uncertainty-aware SM estimation
Minimum Variance (LWF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simple and efficient - Robust to model uncertainty - Easily combined with other methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assumes linearity - May not capture complex dependencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of RS and in situ data - Operational SM monitoring
Machine Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learns complex patterns - Scalable to large datasets - High-resolution mapping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires large training data - Limited interpretability - Risk of overfitting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Downscaling SM products - Data gap filling and prediction

7 References

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